

D2.6

Microplastic Pollution Report (I)

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Deliverable 2.6 Microplastic Pollution Report (I)

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Executive Summary

Microplastics, defined as plastic particles smaller than 5 mm, have emerged as a critical environmental pollutant, particularly in agricultural soils where they pose risks to soil health, crop productivity, and food safety. This study investigates the presence and distribution of microplastics in 18 olive groves across five countries, categorized by management intensity: traditional, organic, and high-density. Soil samples were collected at depths of 10 cm and 20 cm, and suspected microplastic particles were analyzed using Attenuated Total Reflectance Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (ATR-FTIR).

The analysis confirmed 72 microplastic particles, primarily polyethylene (PE), polypropylene (PP), and polystyrene (PS). Spain exhibited the highest concentration of microplastics, followed by Morocco, Greece, Italy, and Portugal. Most microplastics were concentrated in the topsoil (73% at 10 cm depth), with a significant decrease at 20 cm. High-density management practices showed a trend toward greater microplastic pollution compared to organic and traditional practices.

These findings highlight the widespread presence of microplastics in olive grove soils and their correlation with agricultural practices and soil depth. Further research will explore the interactions between microplastics and other soil factors, such as copper and antibiotic resistance genes, to better understand the environmental impact and inform sustainable agricultural strategies.

1 Introduction

Microplastics, defined as plastic particles smaller than 5 mm, have become a pervasive environmental pollutant due to their extensive use and potential hazards (Geyer et al., 2017). These particles are not only found in marine and freshwater systems but are also widely distributed in terrestrial ecosystems (Bläsing and Amelung, 2018; Horton et al., 2017; Rillig, 2012). Due to their ability to alter soil properties, impact soil organisms, and function as carriers for other pollutants, such as heavy metals and persistent organic pollutants, it is substantial to monitor and understand their presence in soils (de Souza Machado et al., 2018; Rillig et al., 2019).

Given the various input of plastics in agriculture, including mulching films, fertilizers (e.g., sewage sludge, compost) and irrigation practice, agricultural soils are particularly vulnerable to microplastic contamination (Boots et al., 2019; Huang et al., 2020; Pérez-Reverón et al., 2022; Rillig et al., 2017; Scopetani et al., 2022). Investigating the presence of microplastics in these soils is essential to understand the extent of contamination and its potential impacts on soil health, crop productivity, and food safety.

The present deliverable constitutes the first estimates of the extent of microplastic pollution by investigating the presence and distribution patterns of microplastics in selected olive groves. The insights gained from this research will inform strategies to mitigate microplastic pollution and promote sustainable agricultural practices.

2 Methods and Materials

2.1 Sample Collection

Selected soil samples were collected from 18 olive groves, categorized based on three management intensities: traditional, organic, and high-density, taken at depths of 10 cm and 20 cm.

2.2 Visual Sorting and Identification

Visual sorting of suspected microplastic particles was conducted in a clean bench environment to avoid contamination. The suspected particles were picked with tweezers and stored in a 96-well microplate. Photographs were taken using a stereo microscope.

2.3 FTIR Analysis

The suspected microplastic particles were further analyzed using Attenuated Total Reflectance Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (ATR-FTIR). Scans were conducted in the wavenumber range of 4000 to 450 cm^{-1} , with four sample scans at a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} . The spectra obtained were examined and compared to reference spectra of known plastic polymers to identify the type of plastic, using the Open Specy online database. A match was considered reliable with the Pearson's correlation coefficient (R) greater than 0.7. Otherwise, manual confirmation of chemical bands and functional groups were performed.

3. Results

In total, 125 suspected particles were picked from 171 soil samples, of which 72 particles were confirmed to be plastic, while the remaining particles consisted of mineral, organic matter, and other materials. The data in the figure are presented as the particle number for each material type. As shown in Figure 1, the predominant plastics identified were polyethylene (PE), polypropylene (PP), and polystyrene (PS). These findings align with the common types of plastics found in soil (Qiu et al., 2022).

Figure 1 Material type of 125 visible particles identified by ATR-FTIR in selected soils. Numbers are particle numbers.

Additionally, a distribution analysis of microplastics among the five countries was conducted. The results in Figure 2 are presented as the number of microplastic particles per kilogram of soil. Spain exhibited the highest concentration, followed by Morocco, Greece, Italy, and Portugal.

Figure 2 Distribution of microplastics across different countries. Results are represented as microplastic particles per kilogram soil (numbers shown on the graph).

As shown in Figure 3, regarding depth distribution, our observations indicate a significant decrease in the concentration of microplastics at a soil depth of 20 cm. The majority of microplastics, comprising 73% of the total, were concentrated at a depth of 10 cm. This pattern was consistent across all countries investigated.

Figure 3 Distribution of microplastics in different soil depths. Results are represented as microplastic particles per kilogram soil. By far the most microplastic particles are in the top of the soil.

Our findings also indicated variations in microplastic pollution across different management intensities of the olive groves, providing insights into how agricultural practices impact microplastic contamination. As shown in Figure 4, high density management practices showed a trend towards higher microplastic pollution compared to organic and traditional practices.

Figure 4 Distribution of microplastics across different management practices. Results are represented as microplastic particles per kilogram soil. There are not large differences, but an initial trend towards HD having most particles.

4. Conclusions

FU has provided evidence of the presence of microplastics and investigated the distribution patterns of microplastics in olive grove soils. The findings indicate that microplastics tend to be more prevalent in high-density managed olive groves and are concentrated in the topsoil layers. These results indicate that olive management and environmental influences have led to the widespread presence of microplastic in these soils.

Moving forward, we plan to deepen our research by analysing more soil samples and then experimentally examine the interactions between microplastics and other factors, for example copper and antibiotic resistance genes. This comprehensive approach will enhance our understanding of the impact of microplastic pollution in olive grove soils.

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